

Appendix 2.6: List of Sacred Natural Sites in Europe and Central Asia (ECA)

Selected list of natural sites in the ECA Region that are also considered Sacred Natural Sites (adapted from (Dudley et al., 2009; Mallarch, Joseph Maria; Papayannis, 2012; Wild, R. and McLeod, 2008); SANASI initiative).

Protected Area Name	Sacred Natural Site Name	IUCN category	Religion/Spiritual tradition	ECA Country	ECA Region
Ağrı Dağı National Park	Ağrı Mountain	IV	Christianity and Judaism	Turkey	Central Europe
Arran Island Marine Reserve	The Holy Island of Arran	NA	Celtic-Buddhism	United Kingdom	Western Europe
Athos Peninsula WHS	Athos Holy Mountain	III	Christian Orthodox	Greece	Western Europe
Buila Vinturarita National Park	Buila Vinturarita	II	Christian Orthodox	Romania	Central Europe
Chania WHS	Monastery of Chrysopigi	NA	Christian Orthodox	Greece	Western Europe
Doñana National Park and Doñana Natural Park	Santuario del Rocío	II	Christian Catholic	Spain	Western Europe
Golden Mountains of Altai WHS	Altai Mountains	III	Sacred to indigenous Altaians and many other faiths (Buddhism, Christianity and Islam)	Russian Federation	Eastern Europe
Kolovesi National Park	Kolovesi	II	Pre-historic	Finland	Western Europe
Lake Inari – Natura 2000 site	Äjjs/Ukonsaari	V	Sámi	Finland	Western Europe
Lindisfarne National Nature Reserve	Holy Island of Lindisfarne	IV	Celtic/Anglican Christianity	United Kingdom	Western Europe
Meteora WHS	Meteora	III	Christian Orthodox	Greece	Western Europe
Muntanya de Montserrat Natural Park	Montserrat	III-V	Christian Catholic	Spain	Western Europe

Protected Area Name	Sacred Natural Site Name	IUCN category	Religion/Spiritual tradition	ECA Country	ECA Region
National Park della Majella	Various names	II	From Pre-historic to Christian Catholic	Italy	Western Europe
National Park of the Casentine Forests	Casentine Forests	II	Christian Catholic	Italy	Western Europe
Natural Park of Rila	Monastery of Rila	III + V	Christian Orthodox	Bulgaria	Central Europe
Park of Garraf	Tashi Ling Monastery	V	Tibetan Buddhist	Spain	Western Europe
Poblet Natural Area of National Significance + WHS	Poblet Monastery	IV	Christian Catholic	Spain	Western Europe
Serra del Montsant Natural Park	Montsant	V	Christian Catholic	Spain	Western Europe
Several National Parks	Via Laetana	Several	Christian Catholic	Italy	Western Europe
Solovetsky Archipelago WHS	Solovetsky Islands	V	Christian Orthodox	Russian Federation	Eastern Europe
Sulaiman Mountain WHS	Sulaiman-Too Sacred Mountain	NA	Pre-historic to Islam	Kyrgyzstan	Central Asia
Uvac-Milesevka Special Nature Reserve	Monastery of Mileseva	IV	Christian Orthodox	Serbia	Central Europe
Vanatori Neamt Natural Park	Vanatori Neamt Natural Park	V	Christian Orthodox	Romania	Central Europe
Yuganskiy Kanthy Nature Reserve	Yuganskiy Kanthy	Ia	Christian Orthodox	Russian Federation	Eastern Europe
	Llanelly	NA	Anglican Christianity	United Kingdom	Western Europe
	Compton Dundon	NA	Anglican Christianity	United Kingdom	Western Europe